

The Interaction of Gelatin Molecule with Molybdate Ions

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The interaction of simple tetrahedral oxoanion MoO_4^{2-} has been studied with gelatin using polarographic (pH 5.57) and equilibrium dialysis techniques at two different temperatures. The apparent intrinsic constant and the average maximum binding sites have been calculated with the help of Scatchard's plots. The values of association constants ($\log K$) have been found to be 3.574 (pH 5.57), 3.563 (pH 7.50) and 3.522 (pH 9.30) at lower temperature while 3.535, 3.522 and 3.477 respectively at higher temperature. The binding sites are suggested to be non-identical at pH 5.57 and 7.50 while identical at pH 9.30. The number of binding sites available for interaction with the molybdate ion is much less than the actual number of cationic groups i.e. 16, 15 and 12 at lower temperature and 14, 11 and 10 at higher temperature, at pH values 5.57, 7.50 and 9.30 respectively. The values of free energy changes were found to be -4.649 , -4.635 and -4.581 at 10° while -4.842 , -4.797 and -4.763 Kcal/mole at 25° , respectively. The values of enthalpy changes were found to be in increasing order. The order of binding parameters and thermodynamic constants suggested that the interaction is pH and temperature dependent. Statistical effects seem to be more pronounced at lower while the electrostatics are at higher molybdate concentration.

THE role of molybdenum in catalysing the biological activity of enzymes¹ and in accelerating the formation of amino acids in plants² is well known. The electron paramagnetic resonance and other studies have been carried out by several workers to confirm its association with the electron transfer process of many enzymes³⁻⁸. Such studies have revealed that molybdenum forms the active constituent of enzymes like other transitional elements in the metalloproteins. Several studies have also been made on model-compounds in order to show the type of bonding in enzymes⁹⁻¹¹. In most of these investigations the thiol groups of enzymes have been shown to be involved.

The existence of molybdenum(VI) as a cation appears to be unlikely, presumably, on account of its complex polymerisation reactions giving highly charged anionic species^{1,2} in acidic solutions. However, Chojnacka¹³ has reported the existence of a simple tetrahedral oxoanion (MoO_4^{2-}) above pH 5.0. In fact the reactions of oxyacids of molybdenum with proteins may provide a means for their isolation. The formation of rubber like polymers between polyacid of molybdenum and gelatin has been reported by Kumar and Sinha¹⁴. Various physico-chemical methods used for the investigation of metal-protein systems have also been employed by Malik *et al.*¹⁵⁻¹⁶ to study the binding of molybdate ions above and below the isoelectric points of fibrillar and globular proteins. In these studies the binding was found to be pH and concentration dependent. Recently they have made a detailed investigation on the binding of molybdenum(VI) with modified and denatured ovalbumin using polarographic and equilibrium dialysis methods¹⁷. These workers have also proved the general applicability of pH-metric method to investigate the polyacid-protein systems¹⁸⁻¹⁹. Comparative molybdate binding studies

of ovalbumin-s heat and alkali denatured ovalbumin have also been made in the soluble²⁰ and insoluble range²¹ employing appropriate methods. The results below isoelectric point have been interpreted in terms of the protein denaturation. In the present paper, the results on the binding of molybdenum with gelatin employing polarographic and equilibrium dialysis methods have been reported. The effect of pH, temperature and molybdate concentration on the binding parameters are also discussed.

Experimental

Protein :

The solution of gelatin (Oxoid, London) was prepared in deionized double-distilled water at 60° . This solution was dialysed in a cellophane bag against distilled water to obtain an isoionic solution. The solution was centrifuged and its concentration was determined by drying a known aliquot in an air oven at $105-110^\circ$.

Reagents :

Ammonium molybdate (E. Merck) was dissolved in doubly distilled water and estimated gravimetrically by the oxine method²². Sodium acetate (0.2N) and acetic acid (0.5N), both B.D.H., were used for the preparation of acetate buffer, 1.0 M ammonium chloride and 1.0 M ammonia were used for the preparation of buffers of higher pH values. 1.0 M potassium chloride (B. D. H.) solution was used for the adjustment of ionic strength.

Techniques :

pH-measurements : The pH-values of acetate and ammonia-ammonium chloride buffers were measured

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using a systronic *pH*-meter. Potassium hydrogen phthalate buffer (*pH*, 4.0) and borax buffer (*pH*, 9.20) were used for standardization of the instrument. For *pH*-measurements gelatin, molybdate and gelatin-molybdate mixtures were mixed with 0.0861 *M* HCl or 0.0605 KOH, the total volume was made upto 15 ml by adding double-distilled water and 1.0 *M* KCl for the adjustment of ionic strength (0.15). Purified nitrogen was passed through the mixtures, in order to ensure inert atmosphere, before making *pH* measurements.

Dialysis experiments: In equilibrium dialysis a solution of known protein concentration (5.0 gm/L) at the desired ionic strength (0.15) in KCl was placed inside an 23/32" visking cellophane bag which had been thoroughly rinsed and finally soaked in KCl solution at the desired ionic strength. The bag was inserted in a glass stoppered tube containing the 'out side' solution of KCl and molybdate ion. The desired *pH* of 'inside' and 'outside' solution was maintained with the help of suitable buffers (5.57, 7.50 and 9.30). Several similar sets of solutions having fixed 'inside' gelatin and different 'outside' molybdate solutions (total volume 5.0 ml. inside and outside) were prepared. The tubes were shaken at 10 and 25° for a time just sufficient to attain the equilibrium. The outside solution was then separated and analysed for its molybdenum concentration²³.

When no precipitation occurred, V_m , the average number of molybdenum bound per 10⁵ gm of gelatin, could be calculated directly as follows :

$$V_m = \frac{Mo_T - Mo_F}{(P)}$$

where Mo_T and Mo_F represent the total and free concentration of molybdenum and (P) is equal to the total molar concentration of the protein. Control studies indicated that molybdenum binding by the tubing was essentially negligible, but a small loss of gelatin always occurred when the tubing was tied off, and the initial volume of the protein was always less than the outside solution. Results are reported at three different *pH*-values (5.57, 7.50 and 9.30).

Diffusion current measurements: These measurements were carried out on a Heyrovsky polarograph Model LP55 in conjunction with a Pye Scalamp galvanometer in the external circuit. An H-shaped polarographic cell as recommended by Tanford²⁴ was used. Purified nitrogen was bubbled through the mixtures and triple distilled mercury was used for dropping mercury electrode. The cell was immersed in a water thermostat at 25 ± 0.1°. The capillary used, had a flow rate of about 2.2 mg./sec. with a drop time of 3.5 seconds. The rate of flow of mercury drops was determined by Lingane's method²⁵. Since the capillary characteristics (*m, t*) have a marked effect on diffusion current (which is directly proportional to $m^{2/3} t^{1/6}$), these factors were, therefore, controlled carefully throughout these experiments.

The following sets of mixtures were prepared for diffusion current measurements :

- (i) Different concentrations of gelatin (0.25-2.25%) were taken in pyrex tubes and 2.5 ml of 0.004 *M* ammonium-molybdate solution was added in each case. The total volume was made to 12.0 ml by adding fixed amount of buffer and requisite amount of water and 1.0 *M* KCl solution to adjust ionic strength at 0.15. The results are given in Fig. 1A in the form of percentage-protein against $id/(id)_0$.

Fig. 1 A & B. Plots of $id/(id)_0$ vs. protein concentration at *pH* 5.57. Curves A and B are for $8.33 \times 10^{-4} M$ and $6.66 \times 10^{-4} M$ molybdate concentrations respectively.

Fig. 1C. Plot of $id/(id)_0$ vs. molybdate concentration for varying concentrations of molybdate and protein fixed at *pH* 5.57.

- (ii) Varying concentrations of gelatin and $6.66 \times 10^{-4} M$ ammonium molybdate were taken in 12.0 ml at an ionic strength of 0.15. Fig. 1B shows the variation of $id/(id)_0$ against protein concentration.
- (iii) Varying concentrations of ammonium molybdate ($1.33 \times 10^{-4} M$ to $33.3 \times 10^{-4} M$) were mixed with 5.0 gm/litre of gelatin in each case. The total volume was kept 12.0 ml by adding fixed amount of buffer and requisite amount of water and 1.0 M KCl to adjust ionic strength at 0.15. The variation of diffusion current ratio with total molybdate ion concentration has been shown in Fig. 1C.

Results and Discussion

Diffusion current

The protein would normally affect both the half-wave potential ($E_{1/2}$) and diffusion current (id) of the reduction wave of the metal ion²⁴. In this case no shift in $E_{1/2}$ of the molybdenum(VI) in presence of gelatin was observed. Tanford's method²⁵, based on the variation of the ratio of $id/(id)_0$ could be applied satisfactorily at pH 5.57. The marked decrease in the diffusion current at pH 5.57 as determined experimentally and shown in Fig. 1 and 2 (for sets (i) and (ii)) provides sufficient information regarding the binding of Mo(VI) to gelatin. Similar type of decrease in the diffusion current of the dyes and molybdate anions in the presence of proteins was observed by Malik *et al.*^{15,17,27}, hence the reduction in the diffusion current of Mo(VI) in the presence of increasing amount of gelatin must be ascribed due to interaction. These findings are in agreement to Tanford²⁴, who believed that when a reducible substance was bound to a protein there is a reduction in the diffusion current and this decrease may be used to calculate the binding constants.

If id and $(id)_0$ are the diffusion currents of molybdenum in the presence and absence of gelatin respectively and C_0 , C_F and C_B the concentrations of total, free and bound molybdenum respectively, then the molar concentration of bound molybdenum to protein can be evaluated with the help of following equations :

$$C_0 = C_F + C_B$$

$$id/(id)_0 = (C_F + k C_B)/C_0$$

$$\text{and } C_B = (C_0 - id/(id)_0 C_0)/1-k$$

where k (the fractional coefficient) is the limiting value of $id/(id)_0$ when so much protein has been added that all the molybdenum is protein bound. The value of k is obtained by an extrapolation method

$$id/(id)_0 = k$$

$$\text{Limit } C_F \rightarrow 0$$

In our studies the value of k was found to be 0.41 from Figs. 1A and 1B at pH 5.57. Figs. 1A

and 1C show sharp breaks with rising concentration of protein or molybdenum(VI). It may be seen that the addition of gradually increasing amount of gelatin results in the reduction of diffusion current of Mo(VI) till it attains a limiting value (k). Constancy in diffusion current indicates complete binding of molybdenum to gelatin.

The data were analysed by means of Scatchard's equation²⁸⁻³⁰

$$V_m/C_F = K_n - KV_m$$

the value of V_m (average mole of molybdenum bound per 10^5 gm of gelatin) is determined by the relation, $V_m = C_B/P$, where P and C_B have their usual meanings. K is the average apparent association constant for the binding at each site and n is the average maximal number of binding sites on gelatin with the same association constant (K). If all the binding sites are equivalent and independent, a plot of V_m/C_F as a function of V_m should give a straight line such that the intercept on the V_m/C_F axis is K_n , as V_m approaches zero as a limit, and the intercept on the V_m axis is n , as V_m/C_F approaches zero as a limit. Deviation from linearity occurs when binding takes place at more than one set of sites with different association constants²⁸⁻³¹. The contribution of electrostatic factors to the interaction²⁸⁻³² or the change in ionic species of reacting species may also produce curvature.

The results obtained are shown in Fig. 2. A linear relationship does not exist between V_m/C_F and V_m . In fact, the Scatchard's plot of the data shows two straight line regions which indicate more than one class of sites³⁰. The intercept of the upper part with the abscissa in Fig 2 yields a value of $n_1=6$, for the number of binding sites in the first class; corresponding the slope- K_1 , gives the binding constant $K_1=0.86 \times 10^4$. To determine the number of sites in the second class and their binding constants, we plot V'_m/C_F Vs V'_m where $V'_m = V_m - \text{no. of primary sites}$, for the results at pH 5.57. This procedure subtracts out the contribution of the primary sites to the data. This is valid when the two classes of sites does not affect binding at the other. This seems to be the case here. From Fig. 3 we obtain $n_2=2.5$ and $K_2=0.38 \times 10^4$ for the second class of sites. Again, the deviation of points above $V_m=2.5$ is either due to a consequence of the change in ionic species of molybdenum³⁴ or due to the involvement of the third class of sites in the interaction. It is not surprising since the dissociation of a weak acid (here molybdic acid) is pH and concentration dependent and is thus a subject of electrostatic effects such as that operative in ampholytes at varying pH. Assuming that there are additional third class of sites then from Fig. 4, the remaining $n_3=45$ sites may belong to the most weaker sites with $K_3=0.05 \times 10^4$. These values of different classes of sites along with their association constants as determined from polarographic data are compiled in Table 1. The smaller number of sites found from the experimental data clearly indicates that only a few groups participate in

Fig. 2. Plots of V_m/C_f vs. V_m for molybdate-gelatin system at pH 5.57. Curves I, II & III are for equilibrium dialysis at 10°, polarography at 25° and equilibrium dialysis at 25° techniques respectively.

Fig. 3. Plots of V'_m/C_f vs. V'_m for molybdate-gelatin system at pH 5.57. Curves I, II & III are same as in Fig. 2.

Fig. 4. Plots of V''_m/C_f vs. V''_m for molybdate-gelatin system. Curves I, II & III are same as in Fig. 2.

TABLE 1—THE VALUES OF BINDING CONSTANT FOR Mo(VI) WITH GELATIN

pH	Technique	Temperature 10°C							Temperature 25°C								
		n	n ₁	n ₂	n ₃	LogK	LogK ₁	LogK ₂	LogK ₃	n	n ₁	n ₂	n ₃	LogK	LogK ₁	LogK ₂	LogK ₃
5.57	Equilibrium dialysis	16	7	3.7	5	3.574	3.954	3.477	2.819	14	6	2.5	5	3.535	3.919	3.602	2.803
5.57	Polarography	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	13	6	3	4	3.584	3.933	3.547	2.792
7.50	Equilibrium dialysis	15	8	5	—	3.563	3.837	3.041	—	11	6.4	4	—	3.522	3.732	3.000	—
9.30	Equilibrium dialysis	12	7	4	—	3.522	3.808	3.041	—	10	6.2	3	—	3.477	3.681	2.903	—

molybdate-gelatin interaction, since the actual number of cationic sites is 87 for 10⁵ gm. of gelatin³⁵. Further information about the nature of the binding was obtained from equilibrium dialysis experiments where it was possible to work at pH-values other than 5.57.

Equilibrium dialysis.

The results obtained at three different pH-values (5.57, 7.50 and 9.30) and at two temperatures (10 and 25°) are expressed graphically (Figs. 2 to 6) as in the case of polarographic method. The association constants and binding sites calculated from Scatchard's plots are compiled in Table 1. Although these

constants at pH 5.57 compare favourably by both the methods, yet the values from polarography was found to be somewhat different from that obtained by equilibrium dialysis. This slight difference is understandable in view of the fact that equilibrium dialysis generally has been accepted as reliable and accurate method for the determination of binding between small molecules and proteins. This can also be explained by the fact that in equilibrium dialysis more time is given for equilibrium while in polarography observations were taken immediately after preparing the gelatin-molybdate mixtures.

Fig. 5. Plots of V_m/C_f vs. V_m for molybdate-gelatin system by equilibrium dialysis technique. Curves I, II, III & IV are for pH 7.50 (10°), pH 9.30 (10°), pH 7.50 (25°) and pH 9.30 (25°) respectively.

Fig. 6. Plots of V'_m/C_f vs. V'_m for molybdate-gelatin system by equilibrium dialysis technique. Curves I, II, III & IV are same as in Fig. 5.

From pH 5.57 to 9.30 a non-linear relationship exists between V_m/C_f and V_m plot and the extrapolation to V_m/C_f (Kn) and the V_m axis (n) are shown in figure 5. The values of binding constants are given in Table 1. The fact that the relationship between V_m/C_f vs. V_m is linear over the range of Mo(VI) concentration studied indicates that a second class of binding sites if it exists at pH 9.30 must have a much smaller association constant than that observed for the primary binding sites (Table 1). A comparison of the binding constants at different pH-values indicates that the

interaction is highly pH dependent. It is considered likely that free cationic groups on the gelatin molecule may be the primary binding sites²⁸⁻³⁰. It may also be inferred that the difference in pK values of the molybdic acid and the reactive cationic groups may account, at least in part, for the difference in binding behaviour.

The various thermodynamic parameters i.e., free energy change (ΔG°), enthalpy change (ΔH°) and entropy change (ΔS°) for the binding have been calculated by the standard thermodynamic procedures. These values are given in table 2. The order of ΔG° values are in agreement with decreasing positive charge and increasing negative charge on protein molecule. The values for enthalpy changes are found to be -1.008, -1.060 and 1.163 Kcal/mole at pH values 5.57, 7.50 and 9.30 which suggested a stronger combination at higher pH than at lower pH . The relationship between

binding and pH indicates that the net charge on protein molecule has great influence on anion protein interaction. Similarly a change of temperature brings change in the binding capacity which may be attributed due to structural changes in protein molecule.

Evidence of interaction from the titration curves of gelatin with molybdate :

The isoionic gelatin was titrated in the presence and absence of molybdate using standard hydrochloric acid and potassium hydroxide solutions respectively. The curves are shown in the form of volume of acid or alkali added vs. pH -values of the resulting mixtures (Fig. 7). These curves of protein, molybdate and mixture are quite apart, hence valuable information regarding the interaction was gained. There was precipitation below the isoelectric point of gelatin, hence more hydrogen ions were consumed, most probably due

TABLE 2—BINDING CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF Mo(VI)-GELATIN SYSTEM

pH	Technique	Temperature 10°C				Temperature 25°C				
		n	LogK	ΔG° Kcal/mole	ΔH° Kcal/mole	ΔS° Cal/deg./mole.	n	LogK	ΔG° Kcal/mole	ΔS° Cal/deg./mole.
5.57	Equilibrium dialysis	16	3.574	-4.649	-1.008	+12.85	14	3.535	-4.842	+12.86
5.57	Polarography	—	—	—	—	—	13	3.584	-4.910	—
7.50	Equilibrium dialysis	15	3.563	-4.635	-1.060	+12.63	11	3.522	-4.797	+12.20
9.30	Equilibrium dialysis	12	3.522	-4.581	-1.163	+12.07	10	3.477	-4.763	+12.07

Fig. 7. Plots of pH vs. volumes of HCl or KOH added. Curves I, II & III are for $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ molybdate, $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ molybdate + 0.6% gelatin and 0.6% gelatin respectively.

to the formation of poly-nuclear complexes, as was suggested by Malik and Arora¹⁶ in the interaction of molybdenum with proteins. Some useful information has also been gained from the curves of ΔpH vs. pH or the vol. of HCl or alkali as well as from $\Delta pH/\Delta V$ against the volume of acid or alkali added (Fig. 8). The ΔpH of molybdate + protein molybdate vs. the volume or pH of molybdate - protein mixtures (Fig. 9) indicated that the change was minimum near the

isoelectric point while it increased upto pH 9.50 and then decreased. These results also go to show that the complexation of molybdate ion takes place upto pH 8.50 and then decreases.

The appearance of maxima at pH 2.80-3.00 in the ΔpH vs. pH curve is similar to the observed in the pH vs. log transmittance curve of molybdate-gelatin mixture¹⁶. This indicates a change of the isoelectric point as well as the point of maximum interaction. On both the sides the abrupt decrease pointed to a change of the ionic species of molybdenum. It is difficult to correlate pH -metric results with those obtained from the polarographic and equilibrium dialysis technique.

From the results obtained different tentative hypotheses can be made regarding the molybdate-protein interaction. The pH -dependent binding constants suggest that cationic sites are the chief sites for binding the anions. Protein deprotonation and enhanced negative charge would cause such pH -dependent results. The persistence of binding at pH 9.30 may be attributed to the guanidinium groups of arginine residues which have a higher value of ionisation constant ($pK > 12$). The total number of binding sites (n) at two temperatures show that all the positive groups are not available for combination. The small number of binding sites thus does not allow us to determine which groups (arginine, lysine or imidazole) are involved in binding with molybdate. These findings are in agreement with those earlier obtained by Malik *et al.*¹⁵ in the interaction of molybdate ions with transfusion gelatin and ovalbumin. Similar type of conclusions were drawn by Craig *et al.*³⁷ in the interaction of ovalbumin with chloroaurate ions below the isoelectric point of the protein.

Our pH dependent result between Mo(VI) and gelatin could thus be explained by assuming an interaction with the positively charged groups. The complex formation between Mo(VI) and histidine⁸⁸ as well as guanidine⁸⁹ further goes to support our results in lower pH range. Towards higher pH the decreased binding may be due to deprotonation of the imidazolium and amino groups while guanidinium groups remained protonated ($pK > 12$). However, owing to the complexity of the macromolecular system it is difficult to find out the exact groups which are involved in Mo(VI)-gelatin reaction.

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Fig. 8. Plots of $\Delta pH/\Delta V$ or ΔpH vs. volumes of HCl or KOH added. Curves I & II are for $\Delta \phi^H/\Delta V$ and pH for molybdate-gelatin system respectively.

Fig. 9. Plots of $\Delta pH/\Delta V$ or ΔpH vs. pH for molybdate-gelatin system. Curves I & II are same as in Fig. 8.

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